

ANALYSIS OF THE COMPOSITION AND DEFORMATION RESISTANCE OF CERAMIC COMPOSITES

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Abstract

The results of research on the production of ceramic composites based on extremely desalinated masses are presented. Compositions of types of fireclay were chosen as objects of research, which performed the function of reinforcement, and liquid glass - the function of binder - matrix. Composite samples were produced by semi-dry pressing followed by structural strengthening - firing in long-term and high-speed modes. The work methodology included a set of methods of chemical and X-ray analysis of silicate materials and standardized testing of ceramics and composites. Features of the chemical and phase composition of fireclay varieties and their characteristics during firing are shown. The effectiveness of using the composition of fireclay varieties to regulate physical and mechanical parameters, including the minimization of shrinkage as a factor in the deformation flow of products, has been established.

Keywords: composite, ceramics, fireclay, composition, firing, properties.

Introduction

The large volume of production and consumption of ceramics of various functional purposes in the world and in Ukraine increases market competition with a corresponding increase in the requirements for the quality of products, among the characteristics of which the degree of deformation is important [1, 2].

It is recognized that the manufacture of ceramic products is connected with the processes of sequential structure formation at the stages of technological cycles [3, 4]. At the same time, among the physicochemical processes of structure formation, deformational ones should be singled out.

In general, deformation processes are an integral part of structure formation during the molding and heat treatment of ceramics [5-7], however, the uneven flow of these processes in the volume of products leads to distortion defects, technological losses, and a decrease in quality. This especially applies to the manufacture of products whose geometric parameters are characterized by a significant preponderance of surface area over thickness.

Analysis of known research and production experience allows determining the main factors of deformation of ceramics in technological processes (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Deformation factors of ceramics

In this regard, one of the perfect ways to minimize shrinkage and the degree of deformation is the use of ceramic composites based on extremely desalinated masses [8, 9], which became the goal of this work.

Experimental part

Research methods and objects.

The work used a combination of modern physicochemical methods of analysis of silicate materials with

standardized tests of the properties of ceramics and composite boards [10, 11].

Determination of the chemical composition of the samples was carried out in accordance with current standards and modern methods [12].

X-ray phase analysis of materials (powder preparations) was carried out using a DRON-4-0 diffractometer connected to a computer through an interface,

which allowed recording of diffractograms in numerical form in the range of 2-70 2θ with step adjustment of 0.05°. The duration of exposure of each point is 6 seconds. The database of the International Committee for Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS) was used to decipher the phase composition.

According to the modern technology of production of ceramic tiles, samples from experimental masses were prepared by semi-dry pressing with drying and firing on industrial flow-conveyor lines. At the same time, firing took place in roller gas furnaces according to high-speed modes: duration of 55 and 65 minutes at maximum temperatures of 1125 and 1200 °C.

All samples, the indicators of which were compared, were fired together in order to avoid a possible difference in the degree of heat treatment.

The objects of research were compositions based on finitely described masses, where varieties of fireclay performed the function of reinforcement, and liquid glass - the function of the binder - matrix.

. Fireclay chosen for research, produced at enterprises of the Potava and Donetsk regions, differs in raw materials and technological parameters of production:

- Luben fireclay (sample L) is a product of grinding ceramic bricks, made of low-melting polymineral clay and fired in a periodic ring furnace at a maximum temperature of 950 °C;

- Chasovyarsk fireclay (sample Ch1) is a special product of firing at a maximum temperature of 1320 °C and grinding of refractory and clay from a local deposit.

The studied raw materials differ significantly in their chemical and mineralogical composition and physical and chemical properties.

In terms of chemical composition, the Luben fireclay sample L differs significantly from Chasovyarsk Ch1 in the presence of silicon and aluminum oxides with a quantitative ratio of SiO₂: Al₂O₃ - 6.1 versus 1.8, a higher content of Fe₂O₃ and alkaline earth oxides CaO + MgO (9.5 versus 1.1 wt. %) and the total amount of oxides RO+R₂O type - 12.4 against 3.7 wt. % (Table 1).

Table 1

Chemical composition of fireclay

Sample code	Content of oxides, wt. %								
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	LOI
L	66,93	10,90	3,04	0,62	7,96	1,54	0,97	1,96	4,50
Ch1	59.53	33.74	1.10	1.03	0.47	0.67	0.69	1.89	0.29

The results of the X-ray phase analysis made it possible to reveal the peculiarities of the mineralogical composition of the studied materials.

The structural features of the studied samples are determined by differences in crystalline phases, their quantitative ratio, and the degree of development of the glass phase.

Thus, a sample of Lubensky fireclay L, made from polymineral fusible clay when fired at 9500C, is characterized by developed crystalline phases of quartz and varieties of feldspar, and the presence of hematite. residues of hydromica and calcite.

Sample Ch1 of the Chasivyarsky fireclay significantly differs from the Luben fireclay in the presence,

in addition to quartz, of the crystalline phases of mullite and cristobalite, which are larger. by the degree of development of the glass phase (by the area of the diffuse halo).

Analysis of the composites characteristics during long-term firing

According to the purpose, ceramic composites were studied, made by the same method of semi-dry pressing from masses that have the same type and quantitative content of binders and the same granulometric composition of fireclay (wt. %): fraction 3÷2 mm - 10; 2÷1 - 10; 1÷0.5 - 25, 0.5÷0.2 - 25, <0.2 - 20 (Table 2).

Table 2

Composition of composites

Sample code	Content of components, wt. %		
	Lubensky fireclay	Chasivyarsky fireclay	liquid glass, (over 100%)
L	100	-	15
Ch1	-	100	15
X	50	50	15

Analysis of the obtained experimental data showed differences in the degree of sintering and physical and mechanical parameters of the studied composites. It was found that when fired for 15 hours in the maximum temperature range of 800-1100°C, the samples are characterized by similar sintering kinetics with

differences in the values of water absorption and density indicators. First of all, this applies to samples using Lubensky fireclay (L), obtained from polymineral clay fired at 950°C (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Dependence of water absorption (w) and density (p) of composites L (1) and Ch1 (2) on the maximum firing temperature

Thus, after firing in the range of maximum temperatures of 800-1000 °C, the obtained composite L is characterized by a water absorption of 19.1 wt. % and a density of 1.95-1.98 g/cm³. Further increase of the maximum firing temperature to 1100°C, the sintering process intensifies - water absorption decreases to 6.2 wt.%, and the density increases to 2.16 g/cm³.

The composite based on fireclay Ch1 is characterized by a water absorption of 11.4-11.2 wt. % and a density of 1.92 g/cm³ after firing in the range of maxi-

imum temperatures of 800-1000 °C, and after the temperature rises to 1100 °C – reduces water absorption to 9.4 wt.% and increases the density to 1.98 g/cm³.

It was established (Fig. 3) that the use of the composition of the studied varieties of fireclay leads to significant changes in the characteristics of the composite. Thus, after firing in the range of maximum temperatures of 800-1000 °C, composite X are characterized by water absorption of 14.9-14.5 wt. %, with a density of 1.83-1.85 g/cm³, when fired at 1100°C - with a water absorption of 11.3 wt.%, with a density of 1.95 g/cm³.

Figure 3.

Dependence of water absorption (w) and density (p) of composite X on the maximum firing temperature

From the point of view of the purpose of this study, the characteristics of the size change - shrinkage of composite samples during heat treatment are important. (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Dependence of the shrinkage of composites on the maximum firing temperature

It is obvious that the examined composites from the extremely described masses are characterized by an extremely low level of shrinkage of 0.05-0.1% in the range of maximum firing temperatures of 800-1000 °C, however, in the case of sample L based on fireclay from low-melting clay, shrinkage increases significantly with increasing firing temperature. When using composition X of fireclay of different genesis, shrinkage is minimized in the range of maximum firing temperatures of 800-1100 °C.

Analysis of composites characteristics during high-speed firing

In accordance with modern trends in ceramics technology, an analysis of the studied composites, made at high-speed firing modes on flow-conveyor lines for 55 minutes at a maximum temperature of 1125 °C and for 65 minutes at a maximum temperature of 1200 °C, was carried out.

The obtained experimental data indicate certain differences in the degree of sintering and the formation of the ceramic structure from the investigated masses during high-speed firing (Table 3).

Table 3

Sample code	Characteristics of composites after high-speed firing							
	Indicators at firing temperature							
	1125 °C				1200 °C			
	shrinkage, l, %	water absorption, w, %	average density, ρ , g/cm ³	true density, γ , g/cm ³	shrinkage, l, %	water absorption, w, %	average density ρ , g/cm ³	true density, γ , g/cm ³
L	3,40	9,2	2,01	2,49	-	-	-	-
Ch1	0,01	10,6	1,91	2,74	0,01	9,3	1,95	2,77
X	0,01	12,3	1,90	2,60	+3,00	6,9	1,83	2,61

Thus, after firing at the maximum temperature of 1125°C, L samples are characterized by water absorption of 9.2 wt. %, with a density of 2.01 g/cm³ and a shrinkage of 3.4 %, but with a limited sintering interval - when the firing temperature increases to 1200 °C, melting and deformation are observed.

Ch1 samples are distinguished by a wider sintering interval and greater deformation resistance: in the interval of maximum firing temperatures of 1125 - 1200 °C, water absorption is 10.6 - 9.3 wt. %, density 1.91 - 1.95 g/cm³ at a low level of shrinkage of 0.01 %.

The structural differences of the composites are revealed when analyzing the phase composition. According to the obtained results of the X-ray phase analysis (Fig. 5-7) after high-speed firing at a maximum temperature of 1125 °C, it was established:

- samples of composite L based on Lubensky fireclay are characterized by the presence of glass phases and the system of crystal phases quartz – cristobalite – feldspar – hematite;
- samples of the Ch1 composite based on Chasovyarsky fireclay are characterized by the presence of glass phases and the system of crystal phases mullite - quartz - cristobalite;
- samples of composite X based on a mixture of the above types of fireclay are characterized by the presence of glass phases and the system of crystal phases quartz – mullite – cristobalite – feldspar – hematite.

Figure 5. X-ray diffraction of sample L (1125 °C)

At the same time, samples of composite X differ from samples L by a greater development of the glass phase (by the area of the diffuse halo) and the distribution system of crystalline phases in it.

Figure 6. X-ray diffraction of sample Ch1 (1125 °C)

Figure 7. X-ray diffraction of sample X (1125 °C)

Conclusions

1. The obtained results of research and testing confirm the expediency of using marginally described masses for obtaining ceramic composites with increased deformation resistance during heat treatment.
2. As reinforcing components of ceramic composites from extremely described masses, it is possible to use varieties of fireclay as by-products of the production of ceramics and refractories.
3. The relationship between the degree of sintering of composite samples and changes in their size - shrinkage as a factor of deformation resistance - is shown, with long and high-speed firing modes.
4. The possibility of minimizing shrinkage and increasing the deformation resistance of ceramic composites when using marginally described masses based on

individual varieties of fireclay and their mixtures has been established.

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